

STUDIES IN INDIGOID DYES. PART XXI. 1:8-NAPHTHAPENTHIOPHENE-PHENANTHRENE-INDIGOS

BY PARESH CHANDRA DUTTA AND SUNIL KUMAR ROY

The present communication deals with the study of thioindigoid dyes derived from phenanthrenequinone and 1:8-naphthoxyphenanthiophene with the object of comparing the colour of these dyes with isomeric dyes, described earlier.

A study of the colour and chemical constitution of thioindigoid dyes derived from phenanthrenequinone and thioindoxyl (this *Journal*, 1932, 9, 99), phenanthrenequinone and benzthioindoxyls (*Ber.*, 1933, 66, 1226; 1934, 67, 5, 1319) has already been made and the conclusion arrived at has been embodied in Parts VI (*loc. cit.*), VIII (*Ber.*, 1935, 68, 1447) and IX (*Ber.*, 1936, 69, 2343). The present communication is a continuation of this work and deals with dyes derived from phenanthrenequinone and its derivatives and 1:8-naphthoxyphenanthiophene, and thereby completes the study of all the isomeric thioindigoid dyes derived from phenanthrenequinone and naphthoxythiophenes. From the earlier investigations it was concluded that the dyes derived from *o*-diketones and 5:6-benzthioindoxyl had the deepest colour, *i.e.*, the additional benzene ring, when fused into the 5- and 6- positions of thioindoxyl molecule so as to be equidistant from the indigo chromophore $>C=O$ and the auxochrome S, was the most favourable position for producing deeper colour in these isomeric dyes. The dyes derived from 1:8-naphthoxyphenanthiophene and *o*-diketones also fulfill this condition of symmetry in the thioindoxyl part and, as such, these dyes are expected to be also deeper in colour. This expectation has been realised and the dyes are all very deep in colour and, in fact, they are the deepest coloured dyes in this series, even much deeper than the isomeric dyes derived from 5:6-benzthioindoxyl (2:3-naphthoxythiophene) as the comparison of absorption maxima given below will show. Of course, in 1:8-naphthoxyphenanthiophene, unlike other oxythiophenes, the $-S-$, $=C=O$ and the reactive methylene group form part of a six-membered ring unlike five-membered one in the other cases studied, and so this six-membered ring, which is the distinguishing factor in this case, appears to have a much greater bathochromic effect than the usual five-membered thionaphthene ring.

1:8-Naphthoxyphenanthiophene undergoes oxidation to bis-indigo very quickly, and so during condensation, the separate acetic acid solutions of the thioindoxyl and phenanthrenequinone and its derivatives were freed from dissolved air by passing CO_2 , and during condensation also, the flow of CO_2 was continued. The dyes obtained are usually deep blue, and dissolve easily in nitrobenzene and pyridine with a blue solution. These are slightly soluble in acetic acid and insoluble in alcohol. Unlike the other isomeric dyes, these are very slightly soluble in alkaline hydrosulphite, and so full shades on cotton could not be obtained. In concentrated sulphuric acid these usually dissolve, producing a red or chocolate-brown colour. The absorption maxima of the two series in xylene solution are shown in Table I for the sake of comparison of colour.

TABLE I

[Nt, Npt, P and I denote respectively naphthathiophene, naphthapenthiophene, phenanthrene and indigo].

Name of the compound.	Absorption maxima.
2:3-Nt- 9'-P-I	575 m μ
1:8-Npt- " "	590
2:3-Nt-9'-(2'-nitro)-P-I	580
1:8-Npt., " " "	625
2:3-Nt-9'-(4'-nitro)-P-I	570
1:8-Npt., " " "	625
2:3-Nt-9'-(2':7'-dinitro)-P-I	575
1:8-Npt., " " "	630

The structure of these compounds may be represented by the following general formula :

In mono-substituted phenanthrenequinones the condensation shown in the 9'-position is only provisional.

EXPERIMENTAL

1:8-Naphthapenthiophene-9'-phenanthrene-indigo.—The separate solutions of phenanthrenequinone (1.04 g.) in hot acetic acid (25 c.c.) and 1:8-naphthoxy-penthiophene (1 g.) in the same solvent (20 c.c.) were freed from dissolved air by passing CO₂ and then mixed together. The mixture, while the current of CO₂ had been continued, was treated with HCl (conc., 2 c.c.) and boiled for half an hour. The greenish brown solution became green and a dark precipitate gradually separated out. It was filtered while hot, washed with acetic acid and alcohol and crystallised from nitrobenzene as a dark chocolate crystalline mass, m.p. > 300°. It is easily soluble in nitrobenzene and pyridine, moderately soluble in hot xylene, slightly soluble in acetic acid and insoluble in alcohol. In alkaline hydrosulphite it is feebly soluble and so a very light violet shade could be obtained. In H₂SO₄ (conc.) it dissolves with a chocolate colour. Its absorption maxima in xylene solution is 590 m μ .

The method of preparation being similar except in the case of 2-aminophenanthrene-quinone condensed product, where the condensation was carried out in alcoholic solution by anhydrous Na_2CO_3 , the compounds with their properties are recorded below in a tabular form. They all have melting points above 300° and dissolve in H_2SO_4 (conc.), forming chocolate-brown or red colour. As the solubility in alkaline hydrosulphite is feeble in all cases, these cannot be regarded as good vat dyes.

TABLE II

1:8-Naphthapenthiophene-phenanthrene-indigos.

Name*	Prepared from 1:8-naphthoxy- penthiophene and	Appearance	Crystallised from.	Absorption maxima.	Analysis Found. Calc.
1:8-Npt-9'-P-I	P	Dark chocolate	Nitrobenzene	590 $\text{m}\mu$	C; 79.61 80.00 H; 3.72 3.59
1:8-Npt-9'-(2'-nitro)-P-I	2-nitro-P	Blue microscopic needles	Xylene	625	C; 71.49 71.72 H; 3.05 2.98
1:8-Npt-9'-(4'-nitro)-P-I	4-nitro-P	Dark crystalline mass	"	625	C; 71.41 71.71 H; 3.11 2.98
1:8-Npt-9'-(2'-bromo) ,,	2-bromo-P	Do	"	620	C; 66.28 66.52 H; 2.89 2.77
1:8-Npt-9'-(2'-amino) ,,	2-amino-P	Bluish violet needles	"	620	C; 76.72 77.03 H; 3.82 3.70
1:8-Npt-9'-(2':7-dinitro) ,,	2:7-dinitro-P	Blue crystal- line mass	Nitrobenzene	630	N; 5.67 5.83

The abbreviations are the same as in Table I.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
L. S. COLLEGE,
MUZAFFARPUR.

Received May 6, 1957.